

The Intellectual Life that Oil Fostered: Exploring the History of a 'Media Ecosystem' in Latin America (1950-1980)

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In the history of the media in Latin America, oil companies played a fundamental role. Established in the continent since the 1920s, but especially active since the 1950s, companies such as Standard Oil –with its subsidiaries Esso and Creole– and Royal Dutch Shell used the media as a key tool to position themselves locally and gain social and political sympathies. Connecting objectives with the geopolitical interests of the United States, Esso supported the transmission of international news in Argentina, Brazil and Uruguay across radio programs, such as *El Reporter Esso* (Klöckner, 2008). Shell and Creole pushed up, in turn, the production of documentaries and audiovisual contents on the history and cultural life of Brazil and Venezuela.

However, the media work of these companies was more extensive and complex. In Brazil and Colombia, Esso also supported the emerging artistic field, sponsoring exhibitions and contests that would help renew the arts in both countries. Esso Colombia also sponsored the 1959 Book Festivals, and the main Novel Prize of the 1960s. Based on its New York magazine *The Lamp*, Standard Oil also maintained the magazines *El Farol* (Caracas, 1939-1975), and *Lámpara* (Bogotá, 1952-1972, 1979-1990), both noted for their material quality and vanguard content (Nesselrode, 2023). Shell also launched its own cultural magazines: *Revista Shell* (Caracas, 1952-1962) and *Vínculo Shell* (Bogotá, 1955-1965), which directed by local academics and intellectuals brought together studies on history, literature, and science.

The national and material specificity of each medium created or promoted by the oil companies has, however, prevented them from being analyzed in its entirety. Although a large part of the oil media did not interact with each other in terms of contents, they were all articulated within a larger strategy of acclimation in different and complex political and sociocultural contexts. Sometimes encouraged by the governments themselves, such as that of Venezuela, which promoted different investments by the oil companies in areas such as education or agriculture, but on other occasions by opening up a space of their own, due to the absence of the State in cultural policy, as in the case of Colombia or Brazil, the oil companies managed to institute a series of media operations of wide scope and influence.

Key to building the reputation of companies among different interest groups, such as politicians, businessmen and intellectuals, but also relevant for advertising purposes among the working and emergent middle classes, the set of media built by oil companies in Latin America demands a study approach that transcends the monomedia vision. Concepts such as 'media ecosystem' seem, in this sense, more appropriate to encompass the complexity and diversity of the media built by the oil companies. Despite the national, technological and production differences, and even the target audiences, literature magazines, films, radio and television programs, along with the cultural activities that the companies also encouraged, such as literary prizes or art exhibitions, coexisted and were dynamically interconnected.

A special case of interconnection and ubiquity is provided by the Filmoteca Shell, a repository of short films created by the company and which operated simultaneously in Caracas, Bogotá and São Paulo. Linked to the public relations offices present in each city, Filmotecas made its films catalogues available to universities, schools, other companies and institutions. Although initially composed of Shell's own films, this repository gradually incorporated films produced independently or those

winners of contest sponsored by the company. Publicized extensively in the different Shell magazines and other news and literary periodicals, the Filmotecas were fundamental places in the promotion of the company's audiovisual work but played in parallel as a kind of 'media libraries' for educational purposes in general publics.

Examples like this show that the oil media ecosystem affected the evolution of the media cultures of each country –complexing to this extent their role as agents of modernization (Colmenares, 2024). On the one hand, it determined new products and forms of audiovisual consumption, and on the other, it influenced groups and actors interested in using the media for academic purposes or artistic creation. The ability to affect professions associated with the media, precisely through the creation or stimulation of new media platforms, constitutes another particularity of the ecosystem. In Venezuela, television news such as *El Observador Creole* (Standard Oil, 1953-1972) were not only key in the transition and familiarization of modern forms of informative communication but also crucial in the expansion of journalists' labor field. Staffed by local journalists with large experience in radio news programs, such as *El Reporter Esso*, the new television program required, however, adaptations that led to early specializations in the profession.

The public relations offices of Esso and Shell were equally relevant in the transformation of intellectual figures into 'mediensarbeiters' (Wagner, 2019). In Shell Colombia, its first public relations director, the journalist Jorge Arenas Lemos, would be the director of the magazine *Vínculo Shell*, publication always admired by their materiality and newer reportages, as well as the producer of the company films. The experience gained would later make him a representative figure of private television production and advertising agencies in Colombia.

The recruitment of writers and poets for public relations positions was, in fact, a constant among oil companies. In Venezuela, *Revista Shell* was headed by young but valued figures from the literary medium, such as the poet Julián Pradón and the politician and publisher José Ramón Medina, while in Colombia Esso would hire writers such as Álvaro Mutis and journalists such as Hernando de Francisco as public relations directors, both of whom were key in sponsoring radio programs and supporting contests and magazines. This practice would even be replicated by national oil companies, such as the Peruvian Petroperú, which had the poet Pedro Roger Cateriano as its head of public relations for a long time, a position that allowed him to create the Copé Short Story Prize in 1979.

By stimulating and recruiting writers and journalist, promoting new practices in public relations, supporting galleries and artists, introducing radio news programs and producing audiovisual content, oil capital represented, in short, a decisive factor in the transformation of the Latin America cultural field. Part of a larger research project, this proposal aims to explore for the first time the 'media ecosystem' built by Oil Companies. Along with reconstructing their origins and multiply fronts, this study explores its impacts within intellectual sphere. Considering the entangled dimension of the case (Cronqvist & Hilgert, 2017), as well as its transnational condition (Lyons & Mollier, 2012), the proposal also reflects on the legacy of this media 'petroculture' in the region.

References

- Colmenares, M. (2024). Después de medio siglo (1966) y el ocaso de la Shell como agente modernizador en Venezuela. *Culturales*, 12(1), 1-41.
- Cronqvist, M., & Hilgert, C. (2017). Entangled Media Histories: The value of transnational and transmedial approaches in Media Historiography. *Media History*, 23(1), 130-141.
- Klöckner, Luciano (2008). *O Repórter Esso: a síntese radiofônica mundial que fez história*. Porto Alegre: Age.
- Nesselrode, Sean (2023). *Refined Material: Petroculture and Modernity in Venezuela*. Oakland: University of California Press.
- Lyons, M. & Mollier, J.-Y. (2012). L'histoire du livre dans une perspective transnationale. *Histoire et civilisation du livre* 8 (nov.), 9-20.
- Wagner, H.-U. (2019). Writers and Radio: How literary authors have made use of the medium over a century. *Journal for Media History*, 22(2), 8-23.